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TAKE-HOME LABORATORY KITS FOR PRACTICAL CLASSES IN THE HOME

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ABSTRACT

With the rapid move to fully online teaching brought on by COVID-19, educators scrambled to redesign and adapt their curricula to ensure that students would receive an educational experience at least on par with what they would receive in an on-campus setting. A major concern with shifting to online delivery, particularly for engineering, is being able to replicate the benefits of experiential learning, usually supported by laboratory classes involving specific technical equipment, in an online environment. Furthermore, due to lockdown conditions and travel restrictions, students would be confined to their homes and unable to attend campus to use any laboratory equipment.

An initiative was devised to send out a laboratory kit out to all students, both domestic and overseas, enrolled in a third year electronics subject that could be used to perform the laboratory exercises in their own home. Synchronous, scheduled online classes provided the necessary structure for the learning activities and demonstrators were trained to supervise these sessions and remotely perform assessment of student tasks. Technical equipment was provided to the demonstrators to specifically support this mode of teaching.

This paper presents and discusses the creation of the take-home laboratory kit, the logistics involved in distributing the kit to students, the management of health and safety issues, and how the laboratory classes and tasks were modified to facilitate the take-home laboratory kits in an online environment. Results have shown an overwhelmingly positive student response to the initiative, supporting a continuation of the scheme into the future.

1 INTRODUCTION

Laboratory-based courses play a critical role in scientific and engineering education. Traditionally, such laboratories have comprised hands-on, face-to-face teaching and learning activities, where students are actively performing experiments, doing design work, gathering data and interacting with specific technical laboratory equipment. In this manner, laboratory classes can be seen as embodying the philosophy of experiential learning [1], which shifts the learning from being teacher-centered, where the teaching is largely transmissive to an approach that is semi-structured and requires students to cooperate and learn from one another through direct experiences tied to real world problems. As technology has improved, in particular computing power, internet bandwidth and video quality, the academic community has embraced alternative methods to deliver these laboratory classes and attempt to provide equivalent experiential learning opportunities through virtual and remote laboratories.

Virtual laboratories utilise software packages to simulate the experiments ordinarily performed in the laboratory class. These types of laboratories do not completely replicate the associated in-class teaching and learning activities but typically provide instruction without any human-to-human interaction and often do not support group work [2]. While there are arguments for their usefulness, particularly in terms of low-cost, ability to be self-paced and opportunity for repetition, their effectiveness compared to learning from undertaking real experimental work is not clear [3]. In particular, positive student outcomes and observed increases in motivation are potentially based more on novelty than design and the effects of reduced social learning are not included in most comparative studies [2].

Remote laboratories aim to address some of the limitations associated with virtual laboratories by incorporating real laboratory equipment in a simulation environment. Typically, students remotely access laboratory equipment to perform experiments and are able to observe the results via a camera or remote interface to the equipment without having to be physically present in the laboratory. Having a direct connection to a real-world piece of equipment in this way can help add to the authenticity of the laboratory experiment. In a similar way to virtual laboratories, remote laboratories support students' autonomous learning activities, however they come at an increased cost in terms of equipment, laboratory space and ongoing maintenance and support [4].

Recently, augmented reality (AR) has offered to improve the experience of virtual or remote laboratories and in some cases has been shown to improve student outcomes [5], however the cost and time to set up such a system could be prohibitive, particularly in courses with large student numbers or when rapid development and deployment is required.

The debate over these different approaches is made ever more confusing by the use of different educational objectives as criteria for judging the laboratories. On-campus advocates tend to emphasise design and build skills, while remote laboratory

advocates tend to focus more on conceptual understanding. The presence of computers in all three of these approaches blurs the boundaries even further [6].

This paper details an approach that is somewhat of a hybrid of the traditional notions of virtual and remote laboratories described above, which was motivated by the need to deliver classes wholly online due to the COVID-19 pandemic. A specially-prepared laboratory kit was sent out to all students, both domestic and overseas, enrolled in a third year electronics subject that could be used to perform the laboratory exercises in their own home. Synchronous, scheduled online classes provided the necessary structure for the learning activities and demonstrators were trained to supervise these sessions and remotely perform assessment of student tasks. Evaluation of the use of the take-home laboratory kits is ongoing and will be the subject of a larger study, however some preliminary feedback thus far is presented.

2 DEVELOPMENT OF THE TAKE-HOME LABORATORY KIT

The COVID-19 pandemic necessitated many universities world-wide to rapidly migrate their teaching programs to a wholly online environment. This forced educators to redesign and adapt their curricula to ensure that students would receive an educational experience at least on par with what they would receive in an on-campus setting. Due to lockdown conditions and travel restrictions, students would be confined to their homes, possibly overseas, and unable to attend the university campus to use any laboratory equipment. Furthermore, strict restrictions on staff attending the campus would mean that all laboratories were shut down and laboratory equipment was unable to be supported or maintained. Under these conditions, the Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering developed an initiative to provide take-home laboratory kits to all students enrolled in a particular set of subjects in order for them to complete the laboratory classes in their own home, in a synchronous online learning environment. This paper focuses on one of those subjects, a third-year electronics subject, and details the kit compositions, necessary changes to the curriculum, assessment activities, class format and logistics and health and safety regulations.

2.1 Online laboratory class format and logistics

Prior to the migration to wholly-online teaching, each week, students would attend their scheduled on-campus laboratory session and design, build and test a circuit on breadboard, under the facilitation of two demonstrators, who would assess their work during the class. Students worked in teams of three, and each laboratory class comprised of approximately thirty students. With the move to online teaching, this model was preserved through the use of the Zoom video conferencing platform which also supported peer interaction within teams. Synchronous classes were timetabled as usual and students would simply log in to the session they were enrolled in by following a hyperlink. Similar to the on-campus class, the demonstrators would discuss the class activities with the entire class using a

webcam and then students would break into their small groups to complete the class tasks, with small group work being supported online through the use of Zoom breakout rooms.

2.2 Take-home laboratory kit contents

The subject previously utilised standard bench-top electrical engineering test and measurement equipment in the laboratory classes – signal generators, oscilloscopes, multimeters, as shown in Figure 1. In order to have students perform the experiments in their own home, the heart of the kit would need to be a suitable platform that would be low-cost, portable and able to replicate the laboratory test equipment. The Analog Discovery 2, shown in Figure 2, was chosen due to its ability as an oscilloscope, waveform generator, power supply, voltmeter, spectrum analyser, impedance analyser, its USB interface and its free, multi-platform interface software. It is highly portable as it can fit in the palm of one's hand and, for the laboratory exercises considered in this subject, could be powered through the USB interface without the need for an external power supply, which could be problematic in other countries with different socket and voltage standards.

Fig. 1. In-class laboratory equipment

Fig. 2. Analog Discovery 2

One of the major limitations of the Analog Discovery 2 is its inability to measure current. Several laboratory exercises required this to be done, so instructions had to be modified to incorporate a test resistor as part of the measurement process, and the current determined by measuring the voltage across the resistor and using Ohm's law.

The passive (resistors, capacitors and inductors) and active components (ICs, op-amps) used in the laboratories were all supplied as part of the kit as well as breadboard for prototyping and hook up wire to make interconnections. The contents of the kit are shown Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Take-home laboratory kit contents

For the digital laboratories, a small DE0-Nano Development Board replaced the much larger DE1-SoC Development Board used on-campus, albeit with a reduced feature-set. This required a redevelopment of the corresponding digital laboratories, however some of the larger board's functionality, for example the seven-segment displays, could be replicated through the Analog Discovery 2.

2.3 Health and safety considerations

As students would be performing the laboratory exercises in their own homes, it was vital that they were able to assess any risks present and ensure that they were operating in a safe environment. The STAR (Stop, Think, Act, Review) process is a method for students to ensure that they are adequately planning their tasks and have considered the necessary safety pertinent to the laboratory. The Environment, Health and Safety (EHS) team, along with academics in the Faculty of Engineering and Information Technology, devised an online survey, called the Take 5 Risk Assessment, that provided a simple, structured way for students to complete the STAR process. Students were required to complete a Take 5 before every class that involved the take-home laboratory kit. This not only had the benefit of ensuring that they had the appropriate procedures and controls in place before commencing the tasks but also gave them insight into considering the risks associated with the particular laboratory, something which would ordinarily only be covered by a single, generic laboratory induction at the commencement of semester.

2.4 Take-home laboratory kit distribution

The lockdown conditions prohibited students from attending campus to pick up the kits. Furthermore, restrictions on travelling outside the home meant that the only way to distribute the kits would be to mail them directly to all enrolled students, both domestic and overseas. The Faculty of Engineering and Information Technology requested bills of materials for each subject employing take-home laboratory kits which were then passed on to an electronics distributor, along with student postal

addresses. Students were asked to complete an online form to indicate the most suitable address to receive their kits, as their circumstances may have changed from when they initially enrolled at the university. The distributor assembled the kits for each subject and mailed them out to the students over the course of several weeks. Due to postal delays, it was essential to begin the mailing out process early so that students would have their kits early in the semester. Students were required to confirm the inventory of the kit they received via an online form and any issues were resolved by mailing out replacement parts.

3 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE LABORATORY CLASSES

The take-home laboratory kits were used in synchronous, online, small-group learning activities with two facilitators (demonstrators). Each class had some individual, assessed preparatory work to be completed beforehand that largely focused on familiarity with how the Analog Discovery 2 was going to be used in the class. Short videos were incorporated into online support modules to visually assist students with setting up their circuits, and to also act as a motivator to get them to prepare for their class.

During the classes, the demonstrators would move between the group breakout rooms on Zoom and provide assistance or explanations as required. Demonstrators were provided with USB webcams, small tripods and headset microphones in order to be able to effectively communicate with the students. When students would complete a task, they would signal the demonstrator to be assessed through raising their hand (virtually) or by sending an instant message. Typically students worked together in their teams and were assessed at the same time as the team. These assessments required students to either be able to show their constructed circuits via a webcam, experimental results via screen sharing, or a verbal explanation of the phenomenon they were observing. This would be expected to take additional time to perform than on-campus classes and therefore was streamlined and simplified where possible.

Instead of a physical sheet of paper to record student marks as was done on-campus, a shared online spreadsheet was used, which provided rapid, real time updating of results and removed one less administrative task for the demonstrators in having to transcribe the marks from paper to the online learning management system.

4 RESULTS

While detailed results investigating the effectiveness of the take-home laboratory classes are still forthcoming pending the completion of the semester, some initial observations can be made:

- Students have reported that they have interacted with the take-home kits more often and for longer than for the total duration of the laboratory classes, as would be the case if they were on-campus. Increasing students' exposure to experiential learning through regular access to the kits in their own time is a

significant positive and can lead to improved engagement and better learning outcomes.

- Demonstrators and students commented that webcams, particularly those integrated in laptop devices, were difficult to manipulate to ensure that they were angled correctly to demonstrate constructed circuits while also keeping the screen visible.
- Students utilised their webcams more often in subjects employing the take-home laboratory kits, even for tasks not requiring direct assessment such as peer discussion, than in subjects that purely relied on virtual laboratories. This is likely due to instilling the use of the webcams as a normal part of the class dynamics from the beginning.
- Debugging incorrectly functioning circuits has been perceived as being more difficult than in-person classes due to the demonstrators having to instruct students remotely via the webcam and not being able to physically verify elements themselves.
- Students interacting with the take-home laboratory kits in their own environment led to some ad hoc exercises in the laboratory classes and lectures where students were asked to locate and incorporate an object in their environment into the class tasks. In particular, the lecturer leveraged the presence of the take-home kits in students' study spaces to have them perform exercises with the kits in real time during scheduled, synchronous online lectures. This is something that is not possible to do on-campus in a standard lecture theatre environment due to space considerations and requiring students to physically carry their kits to every lecture class.
- Students have reported that they felt a sense of ownership and pride over the completed circuits as they did not need to tear them down immediately after the class ceased.

These observations are expected to be strengthened through student surveys performed at the end of semester and an analysis of student results.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The debate about the value of hands-on versus simulated laboratories has been ongoing for some time and will likely continue, particularly now that educational institutions have had to radically reconsider how to deliver their programs. Virtual and remote laboratories each have their own sets of strengths and weaknesses, however take-home laboratory kits could be seen as spanning the gap between these approaches. Such kits provide accessibility, opportunities for experiential learning and motivation to demonstrate self-directed learning and experimentation. With an uncertain future in terms of travel restrictions and the nature of delivery of university courses, it is envisaged that take-home kits will remain a permanent part of the course, providing sufficient flexibility to students to seamlessly participate remotely if the need arises. Even with a wide-scale return to campus, take-home laboratory kits could be distributed to all students to provide an equitable experience

for those who are still unable to travel or who require flexibility in their learning arrangements and to those coming on campus who are able to attend a facilitated laboratory class.

The ready availability of webcams, typically standard on a laptop device, and wide accessibility of high-speed internet across the world has created a simple, yet effective environment for delivering classes in such a manner. Preliminary results have shown an overwhelmingly positive student response to the initiative, supporting a continuation of the scheme into the future.

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